

HOW SHOULD ONE TEACH THE EPIC POEM "HAYRAT-UL ABROR"?

Burkhanova Madinabonu Sayidkamol kizi
Doctoral student of Namangan State University.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15681671>

Abstract: The article details how to teach excerpts from Alisher Navoi's epic "Hayrat-ul abror" given in school textbooks, what should be paid attention to when introducing the work to students, what should be emphasized to make the lesson effective and interesting, and new methods and techniques in the lesson.

Keywords: Lion and Durroj, Hotami Toy, Satisfied and greedy tales, excerpts for memorization, "Writing an essay about the work" method.

The dastan "Hayrat-ul abror," included in Alisher Navoi's "Khamsa," is a moral and educational dastan, calling the reader to maturity. This dastan differs fundamentally from other dastans within the "Khamsa." Also, "Hayrat-ul-Abror" is an encyclopedic work, the main part of which consists of articles and stories, in which the deep moral-spiritual, socio-philosophical reflections of the great thinker on the perfect generation, the perfect man, which are very relevant for all times, are artistically expressed. In "Hayrat-ul abror," the writer's thoughts about a perfect person are vividly reflected in the articles. The stories in the work have a deeper impact on the reader's consciousness of the basic ideas put forward in the articles, allowing them to become better acquainted with the topic.

"An important feature of Navoi's "Khamsa" is that the dastans in it can be read and accepted as independent works, and understood as a whole. The closeness, integrity, and complementarity of these epics lie in their creation based on the most advanced humanistic and patriotic concept, a concept that deepens from epic to epic"¹ Indeed, from the excerpts taken from the dastan, one can acquire a whole world of knowledge and educational concepts. The work leads the reader towards goodness, maturity, and perfection. In particular, as A. Hayitmetov notes, "the first dastan of the "Khamsa," "Hayrat-ul-Abror," has a philosophical and didactic character, and this genre had a history of four to five centuries, perhaps even more, before Navoi. However, following in the footsteps of Nizami and Khusrau Dehlavi, Navoi raised such important socio-political, philosophical-moral issues in his work that he breathed new life into this genre"². Thus, he opposed the robbery of his time, ignorance, and, fighting for good, expressed the following thoughts:

Eyki, qaviy ayladi davlat qo'lung,
Zulm sori tushti va lekin yo'lung.
Zulmung emas erdi xaloyiqqa kam,
Kim qiladursen oni o'zungga ham.

Zulm o'zunga fisqdur, ey hushyor,
Gum qil oni, bo'lsa senga hush yor.
Chunki farah bazmiga azm aylading,
Ayshu tarab azmig'a bazm aylading.
Qasrki, bazm anda muhayyo bo'lub,
Ziynati firdavsi muallo bo'lub.

At the same time, Navoi explains how one should treat parents:

Boshni fido ayla ato qoshig'a,
Jismni qil sadqa ano boshig'a...
Tun-kunungga aylagali nur fosh,
Birini oy angla, birisin quyosh.

When introducing the epic poem "Hayrat-ul Abror" to students, it is possible to effectively use the stories based on the articles in it. Since the stories are mainly in simple, folk language, they are very easy for students to understand. Analyzing each story separately allows the student to get acquainted with different situations, worlds and people. Since this method is effective, three stories from the work are presented to the attention of students in the new 5th grade textbook. They are the stories "Sher and Durroj", "Hotami Toy", "Kanoatli and Tamagir". These stories not only enrich the student's mind and fill it with adventures, but also provide him with moral and educational knowledge. Only in this case, it is necessary to help the student reach the mind through questions and answers and various methods. The following method can be useful in this.

The method of "writing an essay on the work". In this case, students are given the task of writing a short essay on the work. The essay should reflect the sentences corresponding to the content of the work. At the same time, the student writes the essay after reading the work, recalling the work. For example, in the 5th grade, excerpts from Alisher Navoi's poem "Hayrat-ul Abror" are given. After this topic is covered, it is advisable to use this method in the consolidation part. The textbook provides 3 excerpts from the poem "Hayrat-ul Abror". Students can voluntarily choose any of these three excerpts and write an essay. At the end of the lesson, the teacher checks and evaluates the essays.

Topics for writing an essay: 1) An essay on the topic "Lying brings trouble" based on the story "Sher and Durroj"; 2) An essay on the topic "Finding a coin with difficulty is better than a treasure given by someone else" based on the story "Khotami Toy"; 3) An essay on the topic "Patience and contentment are better than greed" based on the story "The Contented and the Greedy".

This method serves to strengthen the memory of students, to draw conclusions from the work, and to increase their competence in writing independent works using the riches of our native language.

Also, there are such bright, special places in the verses of the stories that memorizing them can only be useful for the reader. In the story "The Lion and the Durroj":

Har kishikim rostni bexost der,
Aytsa yolg'on, dog'i el rost der.
In the story "Hotami Toy":
Sen dog'i chekkil bu tikan mehnatin,
Tortmag'il hotami Toy minnatin.
Bir diram olmoq chekibon dast ranj,

Yaxshiroq andinki, birov bersa ganj.

In the story "Qanoatli va tamagir":

Har kishi bu ranjidin o'lsa yiroq,
Sabr-u qanoat boridin yaxshiroq.

Xatqa borib ko'ri bu mastur erur:

"Xom tama' dahrda ranjur erur".

Memorizing these verses will not only strengthen the memory of students, but also help them find the right path in life. The entire work can be a beacon of human life, but a person can become perfect by reading the meanings of just one or two verses of Navoi. That is why this work is being taught from the 5th grade.

Another notable aspect of the stories given in the textbook is that the "Original Text" and "Nose Narration" parts of each story are presented in a comparative form. This allows the student to independently familiarize himself with both the original text and its meanings. The textbook also gives specific recommendations that the latest technologies are used in the lesson meaningfully. Accordingly, "Watch the cartoon "Sher va durroj" based on the story. Source: "Uzbekkino" National Agency, 2010". Nowadays, since information technologies are very widely developed, completing such tasks is convenient for the student and helps to remember.

In order to explain and familiarize school-age students with the epic poem "Hayrat-ul Abror" in whole or in parts, first of all, the text of the work must be selected correctly and in accordance with the student's age and thinking position. Only then can the student become familiar with the text.

Secondly, to introduce the work, it is necessary to effectively use and apply additional tools: questions and answers, tasks. Then, it is necessary to use methods or role-playing games appropriate to the topic presented by the teacher. Only then will the topic be fully covered and firmly established in the student's mind.

List of used literature:

- 1.A.Hayitmetov. "Buyuk she'riy xazina". Hayrat-ul abror.- T.:Adabiyot va san'at nashriyoti, 1989
- 2.Adabiyot. 5-sinf, II qism. Toshkent, 2024
- 3.Azizxo'jayeva N. Pedagogik texnologiyalar va pedagogik mahorat. O'quv qo'llanma. - T.: O'zbekiston Yozuvchilar uyushmasi Adabiyot jamgarmasi nashriyoti, 2006.
- 4.Болтабоев Х. Шарқ мумтоз поэтикаси. – Т.: Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси, 2008.
- 5.Навоий А. МАТ. 20 томлик. Т.16. – Тошкент: Фан, 2000.
- 6.Рез З. Я. Методика преподавания литературы. –М.: Просвещение, 1977.
- 7.SH. Sirojiddinov, D. Yusupova, O.Davlatov. Navoiyshunoslik. 1-kitob. "Tamaddun". Toshkent. 2018